

RAC JOURNAL OF RESEARCH

(Journal of Multidisciplinary Research)

ISSN : 2230 - 7362

Volume 1

No. 14

February 2017

Rani Anna Govt. College for Women
Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India

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Single copy: Rs.300

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A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON GREEN BANKING FOR ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Today ecological preservation and sustainable development are recognized globally in order to protect our planet from the ill-effects of global-warming and climate change. Banks and financial institutions can play a major role in global efforts to mitigate environmental risks and make this planet a better place to live. One step in this direction is Green Banking. Green banking is an umbrella term which refers to those practices and guidelines that make banks environmentally, economically and socially responsible. In an emerging economy like India, environmental management needs to be the key focus area of the business fraternity and especially the banking industry being the major intermediary. This would help the firms in the emerging economies, utilize their limited resources in an optimum way without harming the natural environment and face the global challenge of sustainability in successful manner. In the present paper green banking and environmental management has been discussed in detail. The paper also highlights on the stages, initiatives, benefits and future of green banking in Indian context. Some case studies in Indian context are also being discussed here in order to understand the importance of green banking in the present times. The paper also discusses the various organizations and laws and guidelines for environmental conservation and sustainability and Green Banking.

Key words: Green Banking, Sustainable Development, Environmental Risk, Environmental management

Introduction

The most complicated issue that the world is facing today is climate-change. There have been continuous endeavors across the world to measure and mitigate the risk of climate change caused by human activities. The banking sector is one of the major sources of financing industrial projects such as steel, paper, cement, chemicals, fertilizers, power, textiles, etc., which cause maximum environmental risk. Therefore, the banking sector can play an intermediary role between economic development and environmental

protection, for promoting environmentally sustainable and socially responsible investment. "Green banking" refers to the banking business conducted in such areas and in such a manner that helps the overall reduction of external carbon emission and internal carbon footprint. To aid the reduction of external carbon emission, banks should finance green technology and pollution reducing projects. Although, banking is never considered a polluting industry, the present scale of banking operations have considerably increased the carbon footprint of banks due to

their massive use of energy high paper wastage, lack of green buildings, etc. Therefore, banks should adopt such technologies, processes and products which result in substantial reduction of their carbon footprint as well as develop a sustainable business.

Environmental management in the banking business is considered likely to be risk management. It increases the enterprise value and lowers loss ratio. Therefore, encouraging environmentally responsible investments and prudent lending should be one of the responsibilities of Indian banking sector.

What is green banking?

Green Banking is not a separate bank. Green Banking means ensuring environment friendly practices in banking sector and thereby reducing internal and external carbon footprints. Green Banking therefore covers two aspects.

- The first one being judicious use of all resources, energy and reducing carbon footprints
- Second being encouraging and financing only environment friendly investment.

RBI defines Green Banking as: 'Green Banking is an umbrella term referring to practices and guidelines that make banks sustainable in economic, environment, and social dimensions. It aims to make banking processes and the use of IT and physical infrastructure as efficient and effective as possible, with zero or minimal impact on the environment.

Benefits of green banking

- Green banking avoids as much paper work as possible and rely on online/electronic

transactions for processing so that you get green credit cards and green mortgages. Less paperwork leads to less cutting of trees

- Create awareness to business people about environmental and social responsibility enabling them to do an environmental friendly business practice.
- Green banks adopt and implement environmental standards for lending, which is really a proactive idea that would enable eco-friendly business practices which would benefit our future generations.
- When you are awarded with a loan, the interest of that loan is comparatively less with normal banks because ethical banks give more importance to environmental friendly factors - ecological gains. Natural resources conservation is also one of the underlying principles in a green bank while assessing capital/operating loans to extracting/industrial business sector.

Review of literature

Nath, Nayak et al. (2014) attempt to study the green rating standard given by RBI, the World Bank's environmental and social norms and the initiative taken by bank in adopting green practices. They also list strategies for adopting Green Banking. Green Rating Standard is known as Green Coin Rating. Under this, banks are evaluated on the basis of carbon emissions and amount of recycling activities..

Sudhalakshmi and Chinnadorai (2014) present the status of Indian Banks in respect of Green Banking and state that though green mantra is

essential for emerging economies like India significant efforts have not been taken. Banks are required to include their green aspect in the lending principle. Every step taken today will mean a better global environment in future. So a policy measure to promote Green Banking is needed in India.

Yadav and Pathak (2013) study the Green Banking approaches opted by private and public bank for environment sustainability. Using case study approach they find that Indian banks have understood the relevance of taking positive steps towards the environment. Moreover, results of the study conducted reveals that public sector banks have taken more initiatives as compared to private sector with exception of ICICI bank. In private sector only ICICI bank's approach is a sustainable approach.

Bahl (2012) highlights the means of creating awareness about Green Banking to ensure sustainable growth. Garrett's ranking technique is used to analyze the most significant strategies in respect of Green Banking. If the goal is to attain sustainable development this can be achieved only through creating awareness and imparting education.

Objectives of the study

- To study the concept of Green Banking.
- To identify the steps necessary to adopt Green Banking.
- To create awareness about Green Banking among general public and bank employees.

Environmental impact on the bank

Although banks do not appear to have any direct impacts on the environment, it is not so. Banks play a very crucial role in the society and as a financier to major developmental projects. Their role in the society and impacts on the environment cannot be neglected. Following are the major types of the environmental impacts of the banks.

➤ Internal Impacts

Banking sector is considered as a clean sector which is technologically strong with minimum negative impact on the environment and the society. Direct impacts of the banks are related to the internal operations of the banks that may increase greenhouse emissions, like energy consumption from lights, use of computers and ATM machines, water, waste disposal, business travels etc. The direct impact of banks' energy, waste and paper use on the environment is comparatively less than many other sectors but since the size of the banking sector is large, their impact on the environment as a whole sector cannot be ignored.

➤ External Impacts

It is related to the environmental impacts of banks' products and clients' performance. But the situation is opposite compared to other sectors in the economy. The banks' products are not environmentally unsafe but the clients of the bank who use those products put negative impact on the environment. So it is not easy to estimate the environmental impact of banks' external activities as the banks themselves do not have negative

environmental impact rather the users of these products put negative impact on the environment.

Steps in green banking

The incorporation of social and environmental strategies into the development goals of the banks can help them in arriving an effective environmental management system. As per the empirical study done by Jha, N. and Bhome, S.(May'13), following are some of the steps that can be taken for going green in banking:-

A. Going Online:-Online banking is a new and fast-developing concept in young and corporate India. It helps in conservation of energy and natural resources. Online Banking incorporates:

1. Paying bills online,
2. Remote deposit,
3. Online fund transfers
4. Online statements.

Online savings account and mobile banking is the easiest way to do your bit to bank green and help the environment. Online banking creates savings from less paper, less energy, and less expenditure of natural resources from banking activities.

B. Using Green Checking Accounts:-Customers can check their accounts on ATM or special touch screens in the banks. This can be called as green checking of account. Using a green checking account helps the environment by utilizing more online banking services including online bill payment, debit cards, and online statements. Banks should promote green checking by giving some incentives to

customers by giving higher rate of interests, waiver or discount in fees etc.

C. Green Loans for Home Improvements:-The Ministry of Non-renewable Resource in association with some nationalized and scheduled banks undertook an initiative to go green by paying low interest loans to those customers interested in buying solar equipment. Before you undertake a major home improvement project, study if the project can be done in an eco-friendly manner and if you might qualify for a green loan from a bank. Green loan are perfect for energy-saving project around the house.

D. Power Saving Equipment:-Banks can directly contribute to controlling climate change and as an initial step they intend to start a campaign to replace all fused GSI bulbs, in all owned premises offices and residential areas. Banks can also make a feasibility study to make rain water harvesting mandatory in all the Bank's owned premises. In December 2009 IndusInd Bank inaugurated Mumbai's first solar-powered ATM as part of its „Green Office Projects campaign titled „Hum aurHariyali'.

E. Saving Paper:-Bank should purchase recycled paper products with the highest post-consumer waste content possible. This includes monthly statements, brochures, ATM receipts, annual reports, newsletters, copy paper, envelopes etc. Whenever available, vegetable-based inks are used instead of less environmentally friendly oil-based inks.

F. Green Credit Cards:-Some of the banks introduced Green Credit Card. The benefit of using a green credit card is that banks will

donate funds to an environment-friendly non-profit organization from every rupee you spend on your credit card to a worthwhile cause of environment protection.

G. Use Of Solar And Wind Energy:-Using solar and wind energy is one of the noble cause for going green. State Bank of India (SBI) has become the first bank in the country to venture into generation of green power by installing windmills for captive use. As part of its green banking initiative, SBI has installed 10 windmills with an aggregate capacity of 15 MW in the states of Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra and Gujarat.

H. Mobile Banking:-Mobile banking is tricky. On the one hand, it is great to have the ability to check balances, transfer funds or pay bills from you phone. One the other hand, it saves time and energy of the customers. It also helps in reducing use of energy and paper of the bank. Most of the Indian banks introduced this paper-less facility.

Need of the green banking

Green banking is an integral part of the Bank's environmental policy. The adoption of green banking strategies will help the bank to deal with the risk involved in their business operation(Biswas, N. 2011).

- Create awareness of environmental issues and their impact on the economy, the environment and the society.
- Banks can involve themselves in carbon credit business, wherein they can provide all the services in the area of clean development mechanisms and carbon credit business

- Banks can support projects ranging from community cleanups to national initiatives on climate change, water, air, biodiversity and more.
- In order to implement ecologically friendly practices, banks should launch new banking products which promotes the sustainable practices and also needs to restructure their back office operations.
- Set SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Timely) green goals as the internal targets to reduce carbon footprint along with timelines.
- The banks can manage environmental risk by designing proper environmental management systems to evaluate the risks involved in the investment projects.
- Green banking signifies generating such financial products and services that support commercial development with environmental benefits.

Environmental risk for banks

Banks are exposed to many risks that may lead the banks to face loss in terms of reputation and profit. Banks may not get their money back which they have used to finance their clients and so can face credit risk and reputational risks. So, the risk to the banks from banks' commercial lending activity is high. Thus, besides the liability from the banks' own operations, greater risks are from bank's commercial lending and can be categorized into following types (Weber et al., 2005; Weiler et al., 1997)

➤ **Risk of Loan Default by Debtors**

If the loan debtors violate the environmental legislations, then they have to pay extra cost as a cost of for cleanup. This extra burden of payment many times leads bank clients become financially weak and this makes them defaulters of repaying the loan to the bank.

➤ **Risk of Reduced Value of Collateral**

If the property which the bank has accepted as collateral, gets polluted, then its value deteriorates due to the cost which is paid as cleanup cost. This risk increases the risk of the repayment of the expected amount.

➤ **Risk of Changing Market with Environmental Concerns**

Due to increase in the environmental concern among the customers and release of strict environmental regulations, the survival of the organization without environmental concern is becoming very tough in the present times. Thus, the change in the attitudes towards the environment can make the debtors tough to survive by affecting the banks capability to repay the loan amount to the bank.

➤ **Risk of Bank's Liability**

As banks may have direct business with the collateralized properties, banks become liable for the cleanup of contamination caused by the property.

➤ **Risk of Reputation Damaged**

If the banks do not perform their environmental and social responsibilities then this lowers the credibility of the bank among the public and thus causing loss of reputation of the bank.

Environmental management by banks

Banks play major role in the country's economy and in the sustainable development. Bank being the major financer indirectly contributes to the environmental degradation by financing the projects and the industries whose activities put negative impact on the environment. Thus, the banks by their active participation in the lending business in a judicious manner can contribute greatly to the environment and to the society. Banks are now adopting various strategies where the projects are scrutinized using a set of tools that take environmental considerations. Banks are also encouraging projects that show its concern for the environment in the form of sustainable development, use of renewable natural resources, waste minimization, pollution prevention, occupational health and safety, energy efficiency, care of human health and many similar attributes that tries for the betterment of the society

The bank should also see that their clients comply with the environmental norms while operating their projects and conduct a regular reporting on various environmental criteria. The government should see that there is legislation that can force banks to adopt environmental policy statements and also make the customers aware of it.

Conclusion

Banks are responsible corporate citizens. Banks believe that every small 'GREEN' step taken today would go a long way in building a greener future and that each one of them can work towards a better global

environment. 'Go Green' is an organization wide initiative to lead banks, their processes and their customers to cost efficient automated channels. This will help in building awareness and consciousness about environment, nation and society. All over the world, banks and financial institutions are concerned about the overall impact of depletion of environment. Overall, green banking is really a good way for people to be more aware about global warming and will contribute a lot to the environment and make this earth a better place to live for future generations. There is definitely a huge opportunity in clean, renewable energy technologies, emissions reduction and reduced-carbon transportation which can be slowly and steadily be achieved if we get cooperation from all sectors of the economy and bank being an integral part of our economy must lead from the front. Currently, in India, the concept of green banking is catching up and banks are actively looking for ways to portray themselves as a Green Bank.

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